

THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE MECHANISMS OF ORGANIZATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS BASED ON THE PROJECT APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article is about physical education lessons in high sport school is to teach students about the physical attributes to the introduction of innovative technologies aimed at the development of modern methods of teaching movement, the general classification of the essence, the concept of vision. Physical education theory and methodology of noise that can be used in educational technology in teaching students how to study the concept.*

Keywords: *modern methods, general culture, psycho-physical rehabilitation*

The purpose, importance and features of the physical education lesson. It should be emphasized that the physical culture of a person is a part of human culture, which includes physical and spiritual improvement, professional-practical training, strengthening of health, increase of mental work capacity, psycho-physical rehabilitation and recreation in the process of activity. focused knowledge, skills are integral to the need for physical or sports training.

Physical culture is a part of society, general culture, aimed at strengthening human health, developing his physical abilities, sports achievements.

The legal foundations that determine all areas of public life are reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the Constitution, a person is the highest wealth of society and the state. The purpose, tasks, content, process and results of mastering the subject of physical education should be designed for the student.

This area of culture lays the foundations of physical and spiritual health, which forms a comprehensively developed person. The value of physical culture for an individual and society is manifested in its educational, educational and general cultural importance.

In the next period, the ability to organize one's time in a rational way, systematically engaged in sports and physical education training, internal discipline, intelligence, the speed of correct assessment of the situation and decision-making, determination to achieve the goal set in front of him The term mobilization values is used, meaning the ability to calmly accept success, failure, and even defeat. The realization of the potential of cultural studies in physical education is currently based on the creation of a fundamentally new infrastructure in general education schools.

1) the content of physical education should be in accordance with the characteristics of the development of each school student by age, individual morphofunctional condition, physical education and sports inclinations and interests;

2) use of the latest technologies of physical and sports education;

3) to familiarize schoolchildren with the aesthetic, moral, spiritual and health-forming, health-preserving possibilities of physical education and sports, to form a positive attitude towards the science of physical education in them;

4) to create fundamentally new projects of educational and sports facilities equipped with diagnostic and simulator complexes and means of rapid monitoring of the condition of those who work in them.

The main form or type of basic physical education culture is called "school physical education". This is the formation of general physical education bases and vital motor skills and related knowledge bases, comprehensive development of physical qualities and mental qualities related to them, health aimed at ensuring the optimization of the individual's condition, the achievement of the necessary basic level of physical and general activity necessary for everyone, is considered an educational subject in general secondary schools and other educational institutions is physical education.

The educational subject of physical education helps to develop the personal qualities of students and is a means of forming universal abilities in them. These abilities are expressed in the metasubject results of the educational process and are manifested in various types of activities within the field of "physical education".

Physical education, as a subject of higher education, is an activity that includes such components as information (knowledge), operation (style), motivation (internal need).

The following can be listed as elements of school physical education classes:

- analytical "school of movement" (a system of gymnastic exercises and the rules of their execution, which form the skill of controlling certain movements in a graded manner and the ability to coordinate them in various combinations with the help of such movements);

- mastering the main methods of rationally using one's strength to move on the field, overcoming obstacles
exercise system including (basic ways of walking, running, jumping, etc.);

The goal of the school section of the national system of physical education, (physical education of students of general secondary educational institutions is defined as a pedagogically determined (determinable) vision, oriented towards achieving them, socially based invariant signs of results.

The purpose of physical education classes at school is to support the all-round development of the individual through the formation of the physical culture of the schoolchild. The following are the components of physical culture: strong health, good physical development, the optimal level of motor skills, knowledge and skills in the field of physical education, motivations and acquired methods for physical education, wellness and sports activities (skills).

The target orientation of the organization of physical education at school, taking into account the specificity of the forms of its organization in general secondary educational institutions, is called to reflect a pedagogically simplified vision of the expected results of the implementation of this process.

A clear definition of the degree objective requires:

- its relationship with the target instructions of the national education and physical education systems;

- diagnostics;

- active approach;

- the possibility of leveling (differentiation) forms of physical education of schoolchildren;
- the specificity that grounds the unequivocal perception and understanding of its implementation by subjects (by teachers, heads of bodies dealing with the problems of education and physical education).

In accordance with the socio-economic needs of society and based on the essence of general secondary education, the purpose of physical education is to help to form a well-rounded person.

It is based on taking into account the socio-cultural situation, the demand and experience of general secondary education reform. The main methodological condition for goal setting is that the subject of physical education in the educational system is a part of the educational system, maintaining relations with physical culture, performing educational functions and educational it is mastered in accordance with the laws, principles and requirements of physical education specific to the pedagogical process.

Physical education has specific features and functions related to students' physical health, intellect, and spiritual well-being. As a natural basis of such an effect, the specific characteristics of physical exercises are that they are aimed at certain goals. is considered

Physical education as an element of the educational system is defined as education of the human body - pedagogically correct organization of physical actions directed by the individual.

Physical education includes the following tasks that every student should achieve:

- to strengthen one's health with the help of daily exercises;
- exercise;
- high work ability;
- achieving high life priorities;
- understanding the importance of physical education for health;
- the need to acquire knowledge about hygiene and medicine;
- striving to learn new driving skills;
- the desire to keep one's body in an aesthetic condition;
- understanding the harm of tobacco and alcohol products, etc.

As the most important, quickly recorded humanistic results specific to physical education, physical exercises intended for physical education include health, recreation, rehabilitation, formation of a healthy lifestyle, physical and spiritual recovery, o to involve students in independent physical education activities, the ability of the body to resist diseases, the motor recreation and physical rehabilitation of sensory systems, the knowledge and skills necessary to use the mental and physical work capacity during school for health purposes ' can be noted.

In this regard, knowledge that forms valuable orientations towards a healthy physically active lifestyle and social instructions aimed at achieving it are important. Ultimately, general physical education should form a healthy and, of course, physically active lifestyle. The socially based need to achieve these important results imposes a great responsibility on the physical education subject and teachers.

Physical education is the duty of the system of educational sciences as a subject of the humanitarian cycle related to humanities in the form of an initial didactic framework, which is taken into account when determining the purpose of the educational science. It is embodied in engaging students in activities aimed at objectifying and using the wealth of physical culture and social experience. In the process of educational activities aimed at the objectification of the subject of physical education, they are internalized, the internal process changes again into internal

processes, joins the spiritual world of a person, affects the intelligence and physical health of a person in a complex, creates a multifactorial bio-sociocultural phenomenon - the physical culture of an individual.

The physical culture of a person corresponds to the legal, methodological and didactic foundations of the educational subjects of the same name.

Therefore, the formation of physical culture of a person is determined as the goal of the educational discipline "physical education".

When the goal is to form a well-rounded person, physical education can be evaluated as a system-forming element of the didactic system of "Physical Education" as a result of education.

The purpose of the science of "Physical education" is to perform the task of forming a system, to diagnose the results of the final, intermediate and current stages of the educational process, to manage the education, upbringing and development of students, teaching and learning activities. Motivation consists in creating a positive environment for the interaction of teachers and students. Currently, physical education is of priority due to the health of the growing young generation, the decrease in the indicators of physical development of children and young people. For a long time, physical education, the only lesson in school capable of effectively solving the problem of improving the health of students, was considered a "secondary" subject and was relegated to second place.

The general goal of the science of physical education is to ensure the physical health of every student and its wide application to achieve social success.

The more defined purpose of physical education classes is the development of needs, motives, knowledge, health and abilities of motor organs, normal physical development, movement, physical education and fitness, and acquisition of the basics of sports activities by schoolchildren.

The importance of physical education in the school life of a person is manifested in creating a foundation for all-round physical development, strengthening health, and forming various motor skills and abilities. All this requires the creation of objective conditions for the harmonious development of a person in all aspects. The full development of school-age children cannot be achieved without active physical training. It was found that the lack of motor activity seriously worsens the health of a person, which is becoming more and more perfect, weakens his protective forces, and has an adverse effect on his full physical development.

It is known to everyone that from the physiological basis of physical education, regular use of many physical exercises used in medicine for the treatment of various diseases, rehabilitation of the body, and prevention of diseases has a positive effect.

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